
**Scientific
Report**

2015

LIBR

Laureate Institute for Brain Research
Improving Mental Health Through Neuroscience

IMPROVING
MENTAL
HEALTH THROUGH
NEUROSCIENCE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Letter from the President	4
Mission, Specific Aims, History	8
LIBR by the Numbers	9
Areas of Research	10
Leadership	11
ABCD Study	12
Awards	13
Funding Sources	14
Clinical Collaborators	15
WKW Speakers	16
Visiting Scientists	17
In the News	18
Principal Investigators	20
Ongoing Studies	34
Select Publications	36

The LIBR facilities consist of 28,000 square feet of space in a building that is attached to the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital. The neuroimaging and laboratory facilities at LIBR are *entirely dedicated to research*. They include two MRI scanner bays and a control room, two video-teleconferencing-enabled group meeting sites, several medical examination and patient prep rooms, the computing facility, and ample office space for the investigators.

Details of LIBR facilities:

- 42 offices, including 1 large shared office for students and volunteers
- 4 conference rooms
- 2 MRI bays and adjoining control rooms
- 3 psychophysiological testing rooms
- 1 behavioral observation room
- 2 medical/blood draw rooms
- 1 mock scanner room
- 1 neuropsychological testing room
- 1 transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) room

LETTER FROM THE PRESIDENT

MARTIN PAULUS, M.D.
Scientific Director and President
Laureate Institute for Brain Research

2015 has been an incredibly productive and successful year for LIBR. Our team of investigators has come together and made substantial progress with their programs of research. At the same time, we have had some investigators leave LIBR to move to other prestigious positions both here and abroad. I want to take this time to provide an overview of the accomplishments of the Institute and our continued journey to apply neuroscience to improve mental health.

LIBR has been fortunate to be part of two landmark studies. First, our own Tulsa-1000, also known as the T-1000, will study 1,000 people struggling with problems of depression, anxiety, substance use or eating-related issues. The T-1000 uses comprehensive assessments of individuals to develop tests that can help predict how people will manage over time, estimate risks and help select the best treatments. We have collected data from over 170 individuals over the past year. The LIBR staff has established a very successful strategy for recruitment and retention of these research participants. Our staff scientists have developed state-of-the-art behavioral, biological and symptom-assessment tools to assess the participants. The next step is to begin analyzing the data to identify the best combination of measures to develop the “EKG for the psychiatrist.”

Second, LIBR was awarded a major National Institute of Health grant in September 2015 to be part of a 19-institution consortium, that aims to study the brain development of 10,000 adolescent boys and girls nationwide to determine what puts children at risk for mental health and substance-use problems. Although this study has not yet started, we have been instrumentally involved in setting up the research protocol and are looking forward to beginning data collection in 2016.

LIBR continues to sharpen its focus on how to go about improving mental health. Specifically, we have developed a strategic plan that focuses on three aims. First, LIBR wants to develop neuroscience-based, individually predictive assessments. In other words, we want to provide information to the mental health provider that will make it easier to determine how often to see a patient, what type of treatment to provide and whether the patient is at particular risk for problem behaviors. Second, we aim to develop novel brain-body based interventions. This goal is an extension of our expertise in “interoception,” the processing of information from the body that influences how we we feel and make decisions. To this end, we have set up a floatation clinic, which uses floating (suspending a person in a highly buoyant Epsom salt bath, completely shut off from

outside stimulation) to restore the brain-body connection. Third, we aim to use experimental systems to quickly test assessments and interventions. Experimental systems are time-limited conditions that might put individuals at risk for developing mental health problems. For example, we have set up a study in collaboration with the University of Tulsa to study the emergence of mood and anxiety problems in college freshmen. The goal for this study is to determine whether we can predict who is at highest risk and then intervene to prevent a full-blown depressive episode.

In October, we held our Scientific Advisory Board meeting. Our Board consists of internationally renowned experts:

- Dr. Murray Stein, a leader in the field of studies in anxiety and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).
- Dr. Charles Nemeroff, one of the most well-known psychiatrists in the field and an expert in depression, stress and pharmacological studies.
- Dr. Kerry Ressler, the incoming President of the Society for Biological Psychiatry and an expert in molecular neuroscience of stress and epigenetics.
- Dr. Lawrence Schramm from Johns Hopkins University, a leader in peripheral physiology.

- Dr. Amit Etkin from Stanford, an emerging leader in neuroimaging of anxiety and depression.
- Dr. Mary Phillips, an expert in neuroimaging of depression and bipolar disorder.

We conducted in-person and Skype meetings and received valuable feedback from the Board. In general, they were very pleased with our progress and very impressed by our MRI facilities as well as the high quality of research conducted at LIBR. They made very helpful suggestions for the continued improvement of the Institute and the impact we will have on improving mental health.

LETTER FROM THE PRESIDENT

LIBR investigators play an important role in the Tulsa academic environment and collaborate actively with several investigators from local academic institutions.

(1) University of Tulsa (TU): All investigators at LIBR have a tenure-track faculty appointment at the University of Tulsa, Oxley College of Health Sciences, which brings together several existing TU programs, including nursing, athletic training, exercise and sports science, and communication disorders. Moreover, the investigators have access to graduate students and undergraduate students from the TU departments of community medicine, psychology, computer science and engineering. Professors from the department of psychology collaborate with LIBR PIs on conducting a study focused on neuroscience-based predictive factors for freshman students' resilience to the challenges of college. Dr. Brett McKinney, the William K. Warren, Jr., Assistant Professor of Bioinformatics and Assistant Professor of Computer Science in the College of Engineering & Natural Sciences, closely collaborates with several investigators at LIBR. Collaborative initiatives involve undergraduate students, graduate students and postdoctoral fellows at TU and LIBR, respectively.

(2) University of Oklahoma (OU): Dr. Kent Teague, the Assistant Dean for Research, Director of the Integrative Immunology Center, James Carter Todd Chair of Cancer Research and an Associate Professor in the Department of Surgery. He collaborates with all the investigators at LIBR focused on immune and inflammatory dysregulation in mood disorders. Also at OU, I am teaching students and psychiatry residents at LIBR to discuss research projects with the goal to help conduct research at the Institute and to become familiar with the latest neuroimaging technology. And Dr. Jerzy Bodurka, a tenured Associate Professor at the OU Gallogly College of Engineering, teaches several classes and supervises graduate students working on MR physics problems.

Receiving the grant support to be part of the Adolescent Brain Cognition Development (ABCD) consortium was probably one of our biggest accomplishments in 2015. The objective of the consortium is to establish a national, multi-site, longitudinal cohort study to prospectively examine the neurodevelopmental and behavioral effects of substance use from early adolescence (approximately age 9-10) through the period of risk for substance use and substance-use disorders. Among the overarching research questions:

(1) Within the context of normative developmental variation, what is the impact of diverse patterns of substance use on the structure and function of the developing brain?

(2) What are the consequences of substance use on physical health and development, psychosocial development, cognition (e.g., information processing, learning, memory, decision-making), academic achievement, motivation, emotional regulation and other behaviors?

(3) How does substance use affect the expression (e.g., onset, course, severity) of psychopathology, including substance use disorders, and how does the emergence of psychopathology influence substance use?

(4) What factors (e.g., prenatal exposure, genetic, epigenetic, neurobiological, demographic, psychosocial, familial, ecological) influence the trajectories of substance use and its consequences?

(5) In what ways does the use of specific substances contribute to the use of other substances (so-called gateway interactions)?

It is exciting to be looking ahead over the next 10 years to address some of these important questions.

I want to close with highlighting some of the accomplishments of our investigators:

- Dr. Jerzy Bodurka, the Chief Technology Officer, completed a proof of principle study that showed that neuromodulation can reduce depressive symptoms.
- Dr. Jonathan Savitz continued his work on neuroinflammation and showed that it may be one pathway for developing depression.
- Dr. Justin Feinstein just completed the first functional neuroimaging study of floatation.
- Dr. Robin Aupperle showed in one of her studies that cognitive retraining can be developed as a treatment for PTSD.
- Dr. Kyle Simmons completed a series of studies showing that depression is a heterogeneous disease, and the size of one's appetite may help differentiate subtypes of depression.
- Dr. Sahib Khalsa has established a pharmacological challenge procedure during neuroimaging, that will help unravel the mysteries of anorexia nervosa.

There are several items in the "Good News" column:

- Drs. Jonathan Savitz and Sahib Khalsa received 2015 NARSAD Young Investigator Awards.
 - Dr. Justin Feinstein's work was showcased in *TIME* magazine and he received a grant from the Epsom Salt Council; he was also a 2015 ACNP Travel Awardee.
 - Dr. Robin Aupperle received an outstanding assessment on her K-23 grant proposal, gave an invited talk at the Fire Rescuers International Conference in Atlanta, Ga., and organized Behavioral Activation Treatment for Depression at LPCH.
 - Dr. Kyle Simmons was featured on the Brain & Behavior (NARSAD) website for his high-impact work published in *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, and he submitted his first RO1 grant in June.
 - Dr. Jerzy Bodurka started hyperscanning, i.e., the simultaneous assessment of two individuals in the MRI with the possibility of examining inter-individual brain interactions. This revolutionary approach may help to better understand the doctor-patient relationship.
- Finally, these are some of the significant discoveries made at LIBR in 2015:
- Dr. Kyle Simmons found that there are two different forms of depression—those eating too much or too little—which is linked to specific brain system dysfunction.
 - Dr. Jerzy Bodurka found that self-regulation of emotion in depression is related to shifting brain activation from the right to the left side.
 - Dr. Jonathan Savitz found that inflammation pathway dysfunction is related to several psychiatric disorders (from depression to schizophrenia).
 - Dr. Justin Feinstein found preliminary evidence that shows floating calms brain systems involved in the generation of anxiety.
 - Dr. Robin Aupperle found that PTSD affects the brain systems that are important for stopping dysfunctional thinking.
 - Dr. Sahib Khalsa found that individuals with anorexia do not appropriately interpret body signals.

About LIBR

LIBR MISSION

A clinical neuroscience research institute that recognizes the dignity of each person, and leverages leading talent and technology to discover the causes of and cures for disorders of mood, anxiety, eating and memory.

SPECIFIC AIMS

- Bring to bear a multidisciplinary research program aimed at illuminating the pathophysiology of neuropsychiatric disorders
- Develop novel therapeutics, cures and preventions to improve the well-being of persons who suffer from or are at risk for neuropsychiatric illness
- Foster collaboration among scientists, clinicians and institutions engaged in research that enhances wellness and alleviates suffering from mental illness

HISTORY

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research opened on May 1, 2009, and currently houses a multidisciplinary team of scientists and clinical research staff who apply neuroimaging, genetic, pharmacological and neuropsychological tools to investigate the biology of neuropsychiatric disorders. The Institute's creation was supported by The William K. Warren Foundation for the purpose of conducting studies aimed at developing more effective treatments or prevention strategies for these disorders. The studies are led by scientists from diverse backgrounds, including physics, cognitive neuroscience, psychology, psychiatry, developmental neuroscience, computer science and genetics.

LIBR by the Numbers

Areas of Research

The goal for LIBR is to generate impactful research (knowledge) that makes a difference in mental health. That is, the principal product of LIBR is knowledge building. In order for knowledge to be impactful, it needs to change behavior of the stakeholders and, as a consequence, improve the quality of life of the mentally ill. This change in behavior could be (a) applying a new treatment, (b) providing information to the patient that affects their behavior to improve outcomes, (c) changing the strategy of treatment based on novel assessments, or (d) providing information about likely outcomes in the future. A critical task in creating impactful knowledge at LIBR is to shorten the gap of time between the acquisition of knowledge and the implementation in clinical practice. This gap of time will be greater if production of knowledge focuses on basic processes underlying the pathophysiology of the disorder. Therefore, we need to be mindful of creating knowledge that will affect mental health in the short-term as well as in the long-term.

THERE IS A NEED FOR:

- 1 Earlier detection of the development and/or exacerbation of mental health conditions, e.g., early but not late stages of mood disorder may be treatable with an anti-inflammatory agent
- 2 Sensitive and specific tests for severity of mental health conditions, e.g., predicting relapse may allow the clinician to intervene early
- 3 Earlier and sensitive detectors of treatment effects of interventions for mental health conditions, e.g., rather than waiting 4-6 weeks for an antidepressant to show significant effects, early changes may help to select treatments that work faster
- 4 Detection of emergence of side effects
- 5 More effective interventions for anxiety, depression and substance-use disorders

BEHAVIORAL PROCESSES

This research theme focuses on identifying the physiological bases for drives and behaviors that contribute to the development, maintenance, or recovery from neuropsychiatric dysfunction to improve the assessment and treatment of mental and physical health.

NEUROIMAGING

This research theme focuses on the existing and emerging tools and techniques in multimodal imaging.

NEUROMODULATION

This research theme focuses on real-time feedback modalities to change dysfunctional processes in psychiatric populations.

PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGY

This research theme focuses on the use of physiological measures to examine the connection between body and brain.

BIOASSAYS

This research theme focuses on the use of biochemical measures, ranging from inflammatory markers to microbiome assessments.

LIBR Administrative Staff

LIBR Leadership

Martin Paulus, M.D.
Scientific Director and President

Tom Cooper, MBA
Chief Executive Officer

Colleen McCallum, MBA
Chief Operating Officer

Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.
Chief Technology Officer

ABCD Study

The Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development Study (ABCD) is the largest nationwide study of its kind to date, enrolling 10,000+ healthy children, and following them from age 9-10 into early adulthood. Beginning the study at this age is important, as it is a period of development critical to an individual's life trajectory. The project makes use of scientific and technological advances, allowing investigators to measure brain maturation in the context of social, emotional and cognitive development. This study involves 19 universities and has tremendous potential to influence the fields of psychology, psychiatry, human development and education. The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) was chosen as a study site to enroll 600 youth and their parents.

HEALTHY BRAINS
FOR A HEALTHY OKLAHOMA
Laureate Institute for Brain Research

February 25
How the Brain Grows Up
Marin Paus, M.D.
Psychiatrist and Neuroscientist, LIBR

March 24
Parenting the Tweenage Brain
Amanda Morris, Ph.D.
Professor of Human Development, OSU-Tulsa

April 28
Healthy Body, Healthy Brain
Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.
Associate Professor, LIBR, University of Tulsa

Location
Laureate Conference Center
6655 South Yale
Tulsa, OK 74136

Time
6:00-8:00 pm

For More Info
918-502-5100
info@laureateinstitute.org
www.laureateinstitute.org
www.facebook.com/LIBResearch

TULSA'S LITTLE DRILLER
welcomes all parents, teachers, and learning enthusiasts to a brand new lecture series on brain development in kids!

Awards

2015 Young Investigator Grants Awarded

Two of LIBR's principal investigators have been awarded the prestigious 2015 NARSAD Young Investigator Grant from the Brain & Behavior Research Foundation:

Dr. Jonathan Savitz: "Efficacy of Influenza Vaccine in Major Depressive Disorder"

Dr. Sahib Khalsa: "Augmented Interoceptive Exposure Training as a New Treatment for Anxiety in Anorexia Nervosa"

Congratulations to both on this impressive accomplishment.

ACNP Travel Award

Congratulations to Dr. Justin Feinstein for being named as a 2015 American College of Neuropsychopharmacology (ACNP) Travel Awardee. He was one of 58 recipients from a competitive and talented pool of 338 applicants, the highest and most diverse in ACNP's history.

This accomplishment provided him with a number of benefits for the December meeting in Hollywood, Fla., including registration, lodging, round-trip airfare, an ACNP mentor, a special travel awardee reception and poster session, and an invitation to attend the meeting for the next four years.

Dr. Maurizio Bergamino Receives 2014 Galileo Galilei Award

Dr. Maurizio Bergamino and his co-authors have been named as the 2014 Galileo Galilei Award recipients from the European Journal of Medical Physics - Physica Medica (EJMP). His first-author paper, "A review of technical aspects of T1-weighted dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) in human brain tumors," was selected as the best publication in EJMP in 2014.

Full article reference: "A review of technical aspects of T1-weighted dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (DCE-MRI) in human brain tumors" by M. Bergamino, L. Bonzano, F. Levrero, G. L. Mancardi, L. Roccatagliata, published in Physica Medica, Volume 30, Issue 6, September 2014, Pages 635-643.

In his award letter, the editor-in-chief wrote: "The editorial team felt that this work gives a useful review of the technical issues involved in DCE-MRI in the in vivo study of patients with brain tumors, with a focus on estimating the blood brain barrier permeability. Both theoretical models and experimental procedures are described; particularly useful is the description of data acquisition details, arterial input function assessment and methods for image analysis, so highlighting the role of the medical physicist in the assessment of this diagnostic imaging procedure."

Congratulations to Maurizio on this impressive achievement.

Dr. Kyle Simmons Awarded Tenure at the University of Tulsa

Congratulations to Dr. Simmons for successfully obtaining tenure at the University of Tulsa, Oxley College of Health Sciences.

Dr. Kyle Simmons Elected to ACNP Associate Member

Congratulations to Dr. Simmons for being elected to the American College of Neuropsychopharmacology (ACNP) Associate Member status.

Funding Sources

ACTIVE AND AWARDED GRANTS

National Institutes of Health (NIH)

Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development (ABCD) Study
10/01/2015 - 09/30/2020
PI: Martin Paulus, M.D.

National Institute for Mental Health (NIMH)

The neural bases of pathological food perception and choice in major depression
05/01/2012 - 04/30/2016
PI: Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.

Neuroimaging abnormalities in major depressive disorder: effect of inflammation

09/12/2012 - 07/31/2017
PI: Jonathan Savitz, Ph.D.

Inflammatory transcripts, genes and positive valence system function in anhedonia

09/01/2012 - 07/31/2016
PI: Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.

Effects of amygdala neurofeedback on depressive symptoms and processing biases

04/01/2014 - 03/31/2016
PI: Kymberly Young, Ph.D.

Department of Defense (DoD)

Emotion regulation training for treating warfighters with combat-related PTSD using real-time fMRI and EEG assisted neurofeedback
09/30/2012 - 09/29/2016
PI: Jerzy Bodurka, Ph.D.

Brain and Behavior Research Foundation (formerly NARSAD)

Examining the neural basis of interoceptive fear
01/15/2015 - 01/15/2017
PI: Justin Feinstein, Ph.D.

Interoceptive learning and recall in major depression

01/15/2015 - 01/15/2017
PI: Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.

Clinical trial of real-time fMRI amygdala neurofeedback as a depression treatment

01/15/2015 - 01/15/2017
PI: Kymberly Young, Ph.D.

Augmented interoceptive exposure training as a new treatment for anxiety in anorexia nervosa

01/15/2016 - 01/14/2018
PI: Sahib Khalsa, M.D., Ph.D.

Efficacy of influenza vaccine in major depressive disorder

01/15/2016 - 01/14/2015
PI: Jonathan Savitz, Ph.D.

Oklahoma Tobacco Research Center (OTRC)

Mapping and modifying the influence of interoceptive and reward neurocircuitry in nicotine craving
07/01/2012 - 06/30/2017
PI: Kyle Simmons, Ph.D.

Alpha-7 nicotinic receptor function in depression: the impact of smoking

07/01/2012 - 06/30/2017
PI: Jonathan Savitz, Ph.D.

Oklahoma Center for the Advancement of Science and Technology (OCAST)

Transcranial magnetic stimulation for Mal de Debarquement syndrome
09/01/2013 - 08/31/2016
PI: Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.

MdDS Balance Disorder Foundation

Development of biomarkers to refine neuromodulation treatment targets in MdDS
08/01/2014 - 07/31/2016
PI: Yoon-Hee Cha, M.D.

The Stanley Medical Research Institute

A double-blind trial of adjunctive valacyclovir to improve cognition in early phase schizophrenia
1/1/2014 - 6/30/2016
PI: Sheldon Preskorn, M.D.

Epsom Salt Council

Measuring magnesium absorption via a high concentration Epsom salt bath
03/15/2015 - 12/31/2015
PI: Justin Feinstein, Ph.D.

2015 DONORS

The William K. Warren Foundation	Christopher W. King
Marie Elise Howard Fund	CWK Ventures, LLC c/o Christopher W. King
Floatation Locations	Judith King
The Ironman Foundation	J. Falcon, LTC c/o Judith King
NetworkforGood	Margaret King Kelley
Amazon Smile Foundation	Overall Five, LTD c/o Margaret King Kelley
Roger/Joyce Clark	Constance King Cowett
Sandra Lee	DWK Legacy, LTD c/o Constance King Cowett
Mr. and Mrs. W.K. Warren, Jr.	Natalie Bryant
Michael Barkley	W. Kelly Vandever Revocable Trust
Patsy Lyon	William K. Warren, Jr., LLC
W.K. Warren & Co., L.P.	Stephen K. Warren, Trust A
Warren Charite'	
John J. King, Jr.	
Saxifrage Summit Partnership, LTD c/o John J. King, Jr.	

Clinical Collaborators

We work closely with several clinical entities in Tulsa to recruit new participants to our research studies.

Family and Children's Services (FCS)

Family and Children's Services is devoted to helping families in crisis, serving people struggling with mental illness, addiction and homelessness. They are committed to the families and individuals of the Tulsa area, helping over 110,000 individuals each year, or 1 in 6 Tulsans. As part of our collaboration, one of our LIBR assessment team members is stationed at FCS and regularly recruits individuals to participate in LIBR studies. Also this year, we established a research partnership with the Family and Children's Services program Women in Recovery. The intensive outpatient program is an alternative for women facing long prison sentences for non-violent, drug-related offenses. This award-winning program is dedicated to changing the lives of women in Oklahoma and giving them the tools to become positive, contributing members of the community.

12&12

12&12 is an award-winning leader in the Tulsa community for addiction treatment and recovery services. Last year, they served over 1,600 clients in Oklahoma. This year LIBR established a collaboration with Brad Collins, Director of Community Relations/Research and Efficacy, who helps to recruit individuals with substance-related problems to participate in the T-1000 study.

Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital (LPCH)

Over the past year, LIBR has partnered with our neighbors at the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital to implement a "universal consent" procedure, which enables LIBR to reach out to LPCH patients to inquire about their interest to participate in research. We are hoping to extend our collaborations with other clinical entities in 2016 to be able to obtain a representative sample of individuals with mental health problems from the Tulsa area.

WKW Speakers

DATE	SPEAKER	LECTURE TOPIC
January 6	Amit Etkin, M.D., Ph.D.	Neural Circuits as Substrates of Mental Illness and Targets for Therapeutics
March 3	Jitender Sareen, M.D., FRCPC	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)
April 14	Monique Ernst, M.D., Ph.D.	Choreography of Brain Functions Across Adolescence
May 5	David Glahn, Ph.D.	Searching for Affective and Psychosis Genes Using Neurocognitive and Neuroimaging Endophenotypes
June 1	Charles Nemeroff, M.D., Ph.D.	Neurobiology of Child Abuse and Neglect
October 1	Kerry Ressler, M.D., Ph.D.	Neurogenetic Approaches to Fear and PTSD: From Mice to Man
October 9	Kate Fitzgerald, M.D.	Altered Brain Development in Pediatric OCD: Potential for Clinical Translation
October 21	Daniel Pine, M.D., Ph.D.	Integrating Cognitive Neuroscience and Developmental Psychopathology Research on Anxiety
November 17	Kristen Brennand, Ph.D.	Modeling Predisposition to Schizophrenia using Human Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells
December 1	Beverly Greenwood-Van Meerveld, M.D., Ph.D.	Neuropharmacology of Visceral Pain of Gastrointestinal Origin

Dr. Charles Nemeroff visits LIBR for June 2015 WKW lecture

2016 SPEAKERS

February 2	Angela Vincent, MBBS (Hon Ph.D. Bergen) FRCPATH FMedSci FRS
April 12	Daniel Tranel, Ph.D.
May 10	Alicia Meuret, Ph.D.

Visiting Scientists

LIBR welcomed several visiting scientists to our Institute in 2015.

Dr. Youngkyoo Jung, Ph.D., Assistant Professor, Radiology, Brain Tumor Center of Excellence Comprehensive Cancer Center, Translational Science Institute, Wake Forest School of Medicine, Winston-Salem, NC. "Advances in Arterial Spin Labeling MRI"

Dr. Richard Lane, Ph.D., Professor of Psychiatry, University of Arizona. "Depression, Neurovisceral Integration and the Promise of Real-Time Interventions to Enhance Vagal Tone"

Dr. Marc Wittmann, Freiburg, Germany. "The Inner Sense of Time: How the Brain Creates a Representation of Duration"

Dr. Alan Simmons, University of California-San Diego. "Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging: Processing, Analysis and Interpretation"

Dr. Xiaosi Gu, a computational psychiatrist from the Center for Brain Health at the University of Texas at Dallas. "Your Insula on Fire: A Role of Interoceptive Inference in Decision-Making"

Dr. Tom Foo of GE Healthcare, Chief Scientist in Diagnostics and Biomedical Technologies at GE Global Research. "GE Gradient Coils"

Amy K. Roy, Associate Professor of Psychology at Fordham University. "Severe Emotion Dysregulation in Children: A Dimensional Phenotypic Approach"

Dr. Mark Finlayson, Assistant Professor of Computer Science in the School of Computing and Information Sciences at Florida International University (FIU). "Computational Tools for Analyzing Narratives: Three Levels"

Dr. Jennifer Stewart, Assistant Professor, Queens College. "Neural Alterations in Aversive Processing as a Function of Stage and Type of Addiction"

Dr. Emeran Mayer, Professor in the Departments of Medicine, Physiology and Psychiatry at the David Geffen School of Medicine at UCLA. "Gut Microbiome Brain Interactions in Humans"

Dr. Brian Anderson, Johns Hopkins University. "Linking Reward, Attention, and Psychopathology"

Dr. Shunan Zhang, University of California, San Diego in the Department of Cognitive Science. "Human Decision Making and Experimental Design on Bandit Problems"

Dr. Michael Browning, academic psychiatrist based at the University of Oxford in the UK. "Anxious Individuals Have Difficulty Learning the Causal Statistics of Aversive Environments"

Mahlega Hassanpour, Ph.D. candidate in Biophysics at Washington University in St. Louis. "Developing Diffuse Optical Tomography (DOT) towards Neuroimaging of Speech Perception in People with Cochlear Implants"

Dr. Reese Minshew. "Neither Here Nor There: Trauma, Affect Regulation, and the Role of the Cerebellum"

Brett McKinney, Ph.D., William K. Warren, Jr., Endowed Chair in Bioinformatics at the University of Tulsa, Department of Mathematics and Tandy School of Computer Science. "RNAseq Expression Analysis"

In the News

Risk Prediction Model for Clinical Psychiatry

Dr. Daniel Pine visits LIBR for October 2015 WKW lecture

The July 2015 Viewpoint feature in JAMA Psychiatry between Dr. Martin Paulus at LIBR and Drs. Daniel Pine and Ellen Leibenluft at the National Institute of Mental Health featured a discussion of their replies to the topic: "Biomarkers in psychiatry need to be mechanistic, not simply predictive of course and outcome?"

Dr. Paulus's "No" response: Pragmatism Instead of Mechanism: A Call for Impactful Biological Psychiatry.

Drs. Pine and Leibenluft's "Yes" response: Biomarkers with a Mechanistic Focus.

In Dr. Paulus' response, he highlights the difficulties of making neuroscience useful for clinical psychiatry and advocates for a risk-prediction model in the development of impactful biological psychiatry to help patients now. LIBR's T-1000 study is based on this premise of making an impact on everyday psychiatric practice.

In Dr. Pine and Leibenluft's response, they argue that psychiatry should prioritize studies of biomarkers that include substantial insights about mechanisms, similar to other branches of medicine, to achieve a paradigm shift in how we approach psychiatric illness.

Family & Children's Services BBQ Event

LIBR and Family & Children's Services (FCS) joined forces on Friday, May 29, in Tulsa for our first BBQ event. We look forward to continuing to develop our relationship with FCS, a leading provider of behavioral healthcare and family services for people of all ages in Tulsa and surrounding communities.

Tech Trek Tulsa Visited LIBR

On June 16, LIBR welcomed nearly 40 8th-grade students from the Tech Trek Tulsa STEM camp at the University of Tulsa for a hands-on neuroscience experience. The students rotated through different "stations" to hear about careers in neuropsychiatric research, toured our neuroimaging facilities, participated in a psychophysiology demonstration and learned about neuroanatomy and processing fMRI data.

2015 Zarrow Mental Health Symposium

Drs. Robin Aupperle, Justin Feinstein and Sahib Khalsa shared their current research with the mental health community at the 21st annual Zarrow Mental Health Symposium in downtown Tulsa on September 17, 2015. Their talks were presented during the session on "Integrating Brain and Body to Improve Mental Health." Traditionally, there has been a divide between those investigating (1) brain responses, (2) bodily responses and (3) emotional responses associated with mental illness. A more holistic understanding of neural, physiological and emotional aspects of mental health has the potential to inform our current clinical practice as well as the development of novel interventions. In their presentations, LIBR investigators discussed (1) the role of heart-brain communications in mental health, (2) potential interventions for modulating one's bodily awareness and (3) potential brain mechanisms for current psychotherapeutic interventions. Drs. Aupperle, Feinstein and Khalsa focused on the clinical applicability of neurophysiological research.

TIME Magazine Floatation Feature

Congratulations to Dr. Justin Feinstein for being featured in the *TIME* article "Can Float Therapy Really Treat Stress?" in which he shared how float tanks are engineered to enable relaxation and how he plans to investigate the benefits of floating for people with psychiatric disorders.

TIME Magazine Article Featured Research by Dr. Martin Paulus

Dr. Martin Paulus's work on resilience with Marine infantry platoons and Olympic BMX athletes has been featured in the article "The Science of Bouncing Back" as part of the *Frontiers of Medicine* section in *TIME*.

"By the end of [mindfulness] training, their brains actually looked more resilient," Paulus says. "We were able to show, at least in the brain, that we can train people to modify their brain processes toward the direction of resilience."

Nature Reviews Neuroscience Publication

Interoceptive Predictions in the Brain
Congratulations to Dr. Kyle Simmons and his collaborator Dr. Lisa Feldman Barrett on their publication in the prestigious journal *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*. In the paper, "Interoceptive Predictions in the Brain," they discuss a model of how interoceptive predictions are formed in the brain and how disruptions could function as a common vulnerability for mental and physical illness.

LIBR Investigator Featured by Brain and Behavior Research Foundation

The Brain and Behavior Research Foundation recently highlighted the work of Jonathan Savitz, M.D., Ph.D. in its report on "Immune System Chemicals Linked to a Depression Symptom." Dr. Savitz is a 2009 NARSAD Young Investigator grant recipient. In the featured study, published in the journal *Neuropsychopharmacology*, patients with depression had fewer neuroprotective kynurenine metabolites in the blood relative to neurotoxic metabolites, and the lower proportion correlated with smaller sizes of depressed patients' amygdala and hippocampus, structures that help regulate emotional processing and consolidate memories.

ROBIN AUPPERLE, PH.D.
 Principal Investigator
 Laureate Institute for Brain Research
 Assistant Professor
 University of Tulsa
 raupperle@laureateinstitute.org
 918-502-5744

Dr. Aupperle's research focuses on using neurocognitive and behavioral methods to enhance our understanding of anxiety, depression and post-traumatic stress disorder. She is particularly interested in:

- 1 The neural processes involved in emotional decision-making, which may play a role in the development or maintenance of mental health symptoms.
- 2 Neural and behavioral patterns that may predict response to behavioral treatments of anxiety, depression and trauma.
- 3 How knowledge from neuroscientific research may be used to enhance mental health treatment and prevention efforts.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Aupperle was born and raised in rural Oklahoma and obtained her bachelor's degree in psychology from Oklahoma State University. She received her master's and doctoral education in clinical health psychology at the University of Kansas, under the mentorship of Cary Savage, Ph.D., and Douglas Denney, Ph.D. Her graduate research and clinical education focused on neuropsychology, neuroimaging and anxiety disorders. She then continued out West to complete clinical internship at the VA San Diego Healthcare System, during which her training focused on clinical neuropsychology, cognitive rehabilitation, and treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Dr. Aupperle remained in San Diego to complete a postdoctoral fellowship under the mentorship of Drs. Martin Paulus and Murray Stein, conducting research related to neural substrates of anxiety disorders and PTSD, with a particular emphasis on decision-making processes and treatment. She moved to Kansas City to join the University of Missouri, Kansas City (UMKC) Department of Psychology as Assistant Professor in August 2011. In August 2014, Dr. Aupperle joined the Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) as Assistant Professor.

Dr. Aupperle has initiated research projects at LIBR, investigating neurocognitive and behavioral predictors of treatment response to behavioral activation therapy for depression and exposure therapy for anxiety. In addition, she is taking the lead in LIBR projects—investigating predictors of success for females enrolled in a criminal diversion program and factors related to mental health resiliency in college students.

LAB MEMBERS

- | | |
|---|--|
| Elisabeth Akeman
Science Intern II | Ashley Stillman
Graduate Student,
University of Tulsa |
| Kelly Cosgrove
Research Volunteer | Katie Tombridge
Research Volunteer |
| Steven Green
Postdoctoral Associate | Darcy Waller
Research Volunteer |
| Akalvizhy Elanko
Science Intern II | |
| Nimi Oduleye
Research Volunteer | |

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

- Neural substrates of approach-avoidance conflict decision-making. *Human Brain Mapping*, 36(2): 48-55. Aupperle RL, Melrose A, Francisco A, Paulus MP, Stein MB (2014).
- Neural responses during emotional processing before and after cognitive trauma therapy for battered women. *Psychiatry Research: Neuroimaging*, 214(1): 48-55. Aupperle RL, Allard CB, Simmons AN, Flagan T, Thorp SR, Norman SB, Paulus MP, Stein MB (2013).
- Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex activation during emotional anticipation and neuropsychological performance in posttraumatic stress disorder. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 69(4): 360-371. Aupperle RL, Allard CB, Grimes EM, Simmons AN, Flagan T, Behrooznia M, Cissell CH, Twamley EW, Thorp SR, Norman SB, Paulus MP, Stein MB (2012).
- A reverse translational approach to quantify approach-avoidance conflict in humans. *Behavioural Brain Research*, 225(2): 455-463. Aupperle RL, Sullivan SR, Melrose AJ, Paulus MP, Stein MB (2011).
- Executive function and PTSD: Disengaging from trauma. *Neuropharmacology*, 62(2): 686-94. Aupperle RL, Melrose J, Stein MB, Paulus MP (2011).
- Pregabalin influences insula and amygdala activation during anticipation of emotional images. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 36(7): 1466-1477. Aupperle RL, Ravindran L, Tankersley D, Flagan T, Simmons AN, Stein MS, Paulus MP (2011).

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

- | | |
|--|--|
| Lisa Cromer, Ph.D.
University of Tulsa | Michelle Craske, Ph.D.
University of California,
Los Angeles |
| Amanda Morris, Ph.D.
OSU-Tulsa | Jim Abelson, MD, Ph.D.
University of Michigan |
| Amanda Bruce, Ph.D.
University of Missouri,
Kansas City | Christopher Martell, Ph.D.
University of Wisconsin,
Milwaukee |
| Sandra Billinger, Ph.D.
University of Kansas
Medical Center | |
| Evangelia Chryssikou, Ph.D.
University of Kansas,
Lawrence | |
| Murray Stein, Ph.D.
University of California,
San Diego | |
| Amy Jak, Ph.D.
University of California,
San Diego | |

JERZY BODURKA, PH.D.
 Chief Technology Officer
 Laureate Institute for Brain Research
 Associate Professor, College of Engineering
 The University of Oklahoma
 jbodurka@laureateinstitute.org
 918-502-5101

Dr. Bodurka's research focuses on three main areas:

1 Non-invasive, multimodal neuroimaging method development and applications for studying brain function, including: structural and functional MRI (fMRI), real-time fMRI with neurofeedback, multimodal simultaneous electroencephalography (EEG) and fMRI brain imaging, real-time integration of fMRI and EEG data, simultaneous EEG and fMRI neurofeedback, EEG and fMRI hyperscanning.

2 Novel non-invasive brain neuromodulation and neuroenhancement approaches to better understand brain emotion regulation and social interactions in major depressive disorder (MDD) and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

3 Translational approaches to discover and research novel therapeutic strategies to improve treatments by training and recovering healthy function of brain networks, and to improve psychotherapy by determining the neural features of socially interacting individuals in MDD and PTSD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Bodurka has broad expertise in Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) physics. He received his doctorate degree in physics from the University of Nicolaus Copernicus in Torun, Poland, and completed part of his postdoctoral training in NMR at the Department of Chemistry at Free University of Berlin, Germany. As a postdoctoral fellow at Medical College of Wisconsin, he received firm training in MRI technology and functional MRI (fMRI). As a Staff Scientist at the functional MRI Facility of the National Institute for Mental Health (NIMH) and the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS), National Institutes of Health (NIH), he was responsible for providing a state-of-the-art imaging environment for conducting advanced MRI and fMRI research. In 2007, for his development of a Scalable Multi-Channel MRI Data Acquisition System, he received NIH's Director Award for Advancements in MRI Parallel Imaging Technology. The advancements in MRI receiver and multi-element coils technologies allowed for major improvements in MRI signal-to-noise ratio and pushed spatial and temporal limits for both functional and anatomical imaging. He has also developed an advanced real-time software set-up allowing for conducting real-time fMRI with neurofeedback.

In 2009, Dr. Bodurka joined the newly established Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) to create a state-of-the-art MRI/fMRI/EEG neuroimaging facility and to establish multimodal brain neuroimaging program with the overall purpose of advancing clinical research focused on mental disorders, with a broad research goal of advancing our understanding and characterization of brain abnormalities due to mental illness.

LAB MEMBERS

- Qingfei Luo**
Staff Scientist
- Ahmad Mayeli**
Graduate Student,
University of Oklahoma
- Hasan MD Mehdi**
Graduate Student,
University of Oklahoma
- Masaya Misaki**
Staff Scientist
- Raquel Phillips**
Research Specialist I
- Hideo Suzuki**
Postdoctoral Associate
- Chung-Ki Wong**
Postdoctoral Associate
- Kymberly Young**
Postdoctoral Associate
- Vadim Zotev**
Staff Scientist

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Real-time fMRI neurofeedback training of amygdala activity in patients with major depressive disorders. PLOS One, 9(2):e88785. Young KD, Zotev V, Phillips R, Misaki M, Drevets WC, Bodurka J (2014).

Self-regulation of human brain activity using simultaneous real-time fMRI and EEG neurofeedback. Neuroimage, 85:985-995. Zotev V, Phillips R, Yuan H, Misaki M, Bodurka J (2014).

Subject specific BOLD fMRI respiratory and cardiac response functions obtained from global signal. Neuroimage 72, 252-264. Falahpour M, Refai H, Bodurka J (2013).

Spatiotemporal dynamics of the brain at rest - exploring EEG microstates as electrophysiological signatures of BOLD resting state networks. Neuroimage, 60, 2062-2072. Yuan H, Zotev V, Phillips R, Drevets WC, Bodurka J (2012).

Self-regulation of amygdala activation using real-time fMRI neurofeedback. PLOS One 6(9): e24522. Zotev V, Krueger F, Phillips R, Alvarez RP, Simmons WK, Bellgowan P, Drevets WC, Bodurka J (2011).

Physiological noise effects on the flip angle selection in BOLD fMRI. Neuroimage 54, 2764-2778. Gonzales-Castillo J, Roopchansingh V, Bandettini PA, Bodurka J (2011).

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

- Hazem Refai**
University of Oklahoma, Tulsa
- Peter Bandettini**
NIH/NIMH, Bethesda, MD
- Matthew Feldner**
University of Arkansas
- Wenming Luh**
Cornell University
- Patrick Ladden**
Nova Medical Inc., Wilmington, MA
- Frank Krueger**
George Mason University

JUSTIN FEINSTEIN, PH.D.
 Clinical Neuropsychologist
 Director, LIBR Float Clinic and Research Center
 Principal Investigator
 Laureate Institute for Brain Research
 Assistant Professor, University of Tulsa
 Department of Psychology and Oxley College of Health Sciences
 jfeinstein@laureateinstitute.org
 918-502-5169

Dr. Feinstein's research focuses on three main areas:

1 Develop floatation as a tool for reducing stress and enhancing well-being in individuals who suffer from anxiety.

2 Use functional neuroimaging and the lesion method to help determine the causal source of anxiety in the human brain.

3 Study how the brain dynamically maps the internal world of our body and determine how these maps are dysregulated in conditions of anxiety.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Feinstein's research utilizes the lesion method to explore how the human brain produces primal states of emotion, with an emphasis on the neuroscience of fear and treatments that alleviate anxiety. His laboratory is interested in understanding the intimate connection between the body and the brain, and developing new technologies to help bring this connection to the forefront of awareness.

Every moment of the day, the brain is continuously infused with signals from the internal world of the body, especially the heart, lungs, gut and immune system. The brain attempts to organize all of these signals into detailed body maps, essentially providing the brain with a snapshot of how the body is feeling, moment by moment. It has recently been discovered that disturbances in these body maps form the foundation for a number of psychiatric conditions, including anxiety, addiction and anorexia. Dr. Feinstein's laboratory aims to correct these disturbances by experientially teaching patients how to consciously access their brain's body maps.

Since much of the processing that occurs inside these body maps is happening unconsciously, his lab is exploring several new approaches that can selectively enhance "interoceptive awareness." One approach involves specialized floatation environments, which are highly effective at removing the distractions from the external world so that patients can more clearly experience their internal world. Another approach involves real-time neurofeedback using fMRI and EEG, providing patients with the ability to literally view the brain activity inside their own body maps. Over time, and with repeated practice, these approaches offer patients the unique opportunity to reshape their internal experience and establish a healthier balance between their body and brain.

LAB MEMBERS

- Jesse Schettler**
Graduate Student,
University of Oklahoma
- Will Schoenhals**
Graduate Student,
University of Tulsa
- Colleen Wohlrab**
Laboratory Manager

PUBLICATIONS

Fear and panic in humans with bilateral amygdala damage. *Nature Neuroscience*, 16, 270-272. Feinstein JS, Buzza C, Hurlmann R, Follmer RL, Dahdaleh NS, Coryell WH, Welsh MJ, Tranel D, Wemmie JA (2013).

Sustained experience of emotion after loss of memory in patients with amnesia. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107, 7674-7679. Feinstein JS, Duff MC, Tranel D (2010).

The human amygdala and the induction and experience of fear. *Current Biology*, 21, 34-38. Feinstein JS, Adolphs R, Damasio A, Tranel D (2011).

The pathways of interoceptive awareness. *Nature Neuroscience*, 12, 1494-1496. Khalsa SS, Rudrauf D, Feinstein JS, Tranel D (2009).

Feelings without memory in Alzheimer Disease. *Cognitive and Behavioral Neurology*, 27(3), 117-29. Guzman-Velez E, Feinstein JS, Tranel D (2014).

Preserved emotional awareness of pain in a patient with extensive bilateral damage to the insula, anterior cingulate, and amygdala. *Brain Structure and Function*.

Feinstein JS, Khalsa SS, Salomons TV, Prkachin KM, Frey-Law LA, Lee JE, Tranel D, Rudrauf D (2015, Epub ahead of print).

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

- Ralph Adolphs, Ph.D.**
California Institute of Technology
- Murray Stein, M.D.**
University of California, San Diego
- Hazem Refai, Ph.D.**
University of Oklahoma
- Arthur Janov, Ph.D.**
The Janov Primal Center
- Marc Wittmann, Ph.D.**
Institute for Frontier Areas of Psychology and Mental Health
- Daniel Tranel, Ph.D.**
University of Iowa
- David Rudrauf, Ph.D.**
Grenoble Institute of Neuroscience
- Kaveh Ashenayi, Ph.D.**
University of Tulsa
- Scott Moseman, M.D.**
Medical Director, Laureate Eating Disorders
- Rene Hurlmann, M.D., Ph.D.**
University of Bonn
- Jamie Rhudy, Ph.D.**
University of Tulsa
- William Potter, Ph.D.**
University of Tulsa
- Jacopo Annese, Ph.D.**
The Brain Observatory and
The Institute for Brain and Society
- Ricardo Gil-da-Costa, Ph.D.**
CEO of NeuroVerse

SAHIB KHALSA, M.D., PH.D.
 Director of Clinical Studies
 Laureate Institute for Brain Research
 Assistant Professor
 Faculty of Community Medicine, University of Tulsa
 skhalsa@laureateinstitute.org
 918-502-5743

Dr. Khalsa's research explores three main questions:

1 How do we feel our heartbeat?

2 Is there dysfunctional cross talk between the heart and brain in psychiatric and cardiovascular illnesses?

3 How can we develop new treatments that re-establish a functional dialogue between the heart and brain?

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Khalsa received a B.S. in psychology from SUNY Stony Brook in 2002. He graduated from the Medical Scientist Training Program at the University of Iowa, receiving M.D. and Ph.D. (neuroscience) degrees in 2009. He completed his residency training in psychiatry at UCLA in 2013, serving as the program Chief Resident and Chief Resident in the UCLA Anxiety Disorders Clinic. At that time, he joined the department as a faculty member in the Division of Adult Psychiatry at UCLA, becoming an Assistant Professor in Residence in 2014.

Dr. Khalsa's research examines how people feel their heartbeat, how the human brain maps cardiac sensation, and whether there is dysfunctional cross talk between the heart and brain in psychiatric and cardiovascular illnesses. To approach these questions, his studies have examined the effects of aging, focal brain injury, cardiac dysfunction, and long-term meditation practice on awareness of the heartbeat. Ongoing projects examine the neural basis of cardiac sensation, the neural basis of dysfunctional heart-brain communication in anorexia nervosa and the impact of implantable cardioverter defibrillators (ICD) on awareness of the heartbeat. These studies aim to ultimately answer the question "How can we develop new treatments that re-establish a functional dialogue between the heart and brain?"

Dr. Khalsa's clinical expertise focuses on the assessment and treatment of anxiety disorders. As a faculty member, Dr. Khalsa served as Associate Director of the UCLA Anxiety Disorders Clinic, supervising resident physicians in the treatment of anxiety disorders. As founding director of the Healthy Hearts Behavioral Medicine Program, an interdisciplinary endeavor started with the UCLA Cardiac Arrhythmia Center, he specializes in treating anxiety and mood disorders in individuals with cardiovascular disease who have received ICDs. He also worked as an attending psychiatrist in the UCLA OCD Intensive Outpatient Program.

In February 2015, Dr. Khalsa joined the Laureate Institute for Brain Research as the Director of Clinical Studies, and as an Assistant Professor (tenure track) on the Faculty of Community Medicine at the University of Tulsa.

LAB MEMBERS

- Mahlega Hassanpour, Ph.D.**
Postdoctoral Associate
- Rachel Lapidus**
Graduate Student,
University of Tulsa
- Valerie Upshaw, R.N.**
Clinical Research Coordinator

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

- Altered interoceptive awareness in anorexia nervosa: effects of meal anticipation, consumption and bodily arousal. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*. Khalsa SS, Craske MG, Li W, Vangala S, Strober M, Feusner JD (2015).
- The pathways of interoceptive awareness. *Nature Neuroscience*, 12: 1494-6. Khalsa SS, Rudrauf D, Feinstein JS, Tranel D (2009).
- Current Diagnosis and Treatment of Anxiety Disorders. *Pharmacy and Therapeutics*, 38: 30-57. Bystritsky A, Khalsa SS, Schiffman J, Cameron M (2013).
- Synergistic application of cardiac sympathetic decentralization and comprehensive psychiatric treatment in the management of anxiety and electrical storm. *Frontiers in Integrative Neuroscience*, 7:1-14. Khalsa SS, Shahabi L, Ajjola OA, Bystritsky A, Naliboff BD, Shivkumar K (2014).
- The effect of meditation on regulation of internal body states. *Front Psychol*. Jul 7;6:924. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00924. eCollection. Khalsa SS, Rudrauf D, Davidson RJ, Tranel D (2015).
- Interoceptive awareness in experienced meditators. *Psychophysiology*, 45:671-8 (2008).
- Khalsa SS, Rudrauf D, Damasio AR, Davidson RJ, Lutz A, Tranel D (2008).
- Preserved emotional awareness of pain in a patient with extensive bilateral damage to the insula, anterior cingulate, and amygdala. *Brain Structure and Function*. Feinstein, JS, Khalsa SS, Salomons TV, Prkachin KM, Frey-Law LA, Lee JE, Tranel D, Rudrauf D (2015).

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

- Ralph Adolphs, Ph.D.**
California Institute of Technology
- Richard Lane, M.D., Ph.D.**
University of Arizona
- David Rudrauf, Ph.D.**
University of Geneva
- Daniel Tranel, Ph.D.**
University of Iowa
- Danny JJ Wang, Ph.D.**
University of California, Los Angeles
- Olujimi Ajjola, M.D., Ph.D.**
University of California, Los Angeles
- Michelle Craske, Ph.D.**
University of California, Los Angeles
- Jamie Feusner, M.D.**
University of California, Los Angeles
- Kalyanam Shivkumar, M.D., Ph.D.**
University of California, Los Angeles
- Rene Hurlmann, M.D., Ph.D.**
University of Bonn
- Alexander Bystritsky, M.D., Ph.D.**
University of California, Los Angeles

MARTIN PAULUS, M.D.
 Scientific Director and President
 Laureate Institute for Brain Research
 mpaulus@laureateinstitute.org
 918-502-5120

Dr. Paulus's research focuses on three main areas:

- 1** Using neuroimaging to develop predictive biomarkers for anxiety disorders and addictive disorders.
- 2** Using computational psychiatry to better quantify the behavioral dysfunctions in individuals with mood, anxiety and addictive disorders.
- 3** Develop a research pipeline that enables one to translate basic neuroscience discoveries into clinically useful tools.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Paulus studied Medicine at the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz from 1979-1985. He received a postdoctoral fellowship from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation) in 1986 to study the effects of calcium antagonists on animal models of mania at the University of California San Diego (UCSD). In 1993, Dr. Paulus left UCSD to resume his medical training and completed his internship at the Long Island Jewish Medical Center/Zucker Hillside Hospital on Long Island, NY. In 1994, he rejoined the Department of Psychiatry at UCSD as a psychiatric resident. Dr. Paulus completed his residency in psychiatry in 1997. At that time, he joined the Department of Psychiatry at UCSD as an Assistant Professor and became a staff psychiatrist at the Veterans Affairs San Diego Health Care System (VASDHS). In May 2014, Dr. Paulus joined the Laureate Institute For Brain Research (LIBR) as the Scientific Director and President.

Dr. Paulus has published over 250 scientific papers, has been funded continuously by federal grants since 1997, and is currently the Principal Investigator on a NIMH R01 aimed at determining the biological basis for positive and negative valence domains in anxiety and depression. He has served on numerous research panels, study sections and advisory committees. Currently, Dr. Paulus is conducting a large-scale study in Tulsa, the T-1000, to determine whether biological measures can be developed to help a clinician predict patient outcomes. Dr. Paulus is also a member of the Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development (ABCD) study, which aims to determine how the brain changes during the course of adolescence and how these changes put adolescents at risk for substance use.

LAB MEMBERS

- Maurizio Bergamino, Ph.D.**
Staff Scientist
- Hamed Ekhtiari, M.D.**
Postdoctoral Associate
- Crane Huang, Ph.D.**
Postdoctoral Associate
- Rayus Kuplicki, Ph.D.**
Staff Scientist
- Han Li, M.S.**
Research Intern II
- Teresa Victor, Ph.D.**
Staff Scientist

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS (IN 2015)

- McAllister TW, Zafonte R, Jain S, et al. Randomized Placebo-Controlled Trial of Methylphenidate or Galantamine for Persistent Emotional and Cognitive Symptoms Associated with PTSD and/or Traumatic Brain Injury. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. Sep 11 2015.
- Huang H, Movellan J, Paulus MP, Harle KM. The Influence of Depression on Cognitive Control: Disambiguating Approach and Avoidance Tendencies. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(11):e0143714.
- Paulus MP, Aupperle R. Finding the Balance Between Safety and Threat May Hold the Key to Success When Treating PTSD. *Am J Psychiatry*. Dec 1 2015;172(12):1173-1175.
- Paulus MP. Neural Basis of Mindfulness Interventions that Moderate the Impact of Stress on the Brain. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. Jan 2016;41(1):373.
- Harle KM, Stewart JL, Zhang S, Tapert SF, Yu AJ, Paulus MP. Bayesian neural adjustment of inhibitory control predicts emergence of problem stimulant use. *Brain*. Sep 3 2015.
- Paulus MP. Pragmatism instead of mechanism: A call for impactful biological psychiatry. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2015.
- Gowin JL, Ball TM, Wittmann M, Tapert SF, Paulus MP. Individualized relapse prediction: Personality measures and striatal and insular activity during reward-processing robustly predict relapse. *Drug Alcohol Depend*. Apr 30 2015.

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

- | | |
|--|---|
| Marc Wittmann
Institut für Grenzgebiete der Psychologie und Psychohygiene | Walter Kaye
University of California, San Diego |
| Guilia Galli
University of Chicago | Murray B Stein
University of California, San Diego |
| Tony Yang
University of California, San Francisco | Piotr Winkielman
University of California, San Diego |
| Lawrence Frank
University of California, San Diego | Jennifer Lorraine Stewart
City University of New York, Department of Psychology |
| Alan N Simmons
University of California, San Diego | Greg Fonzo
Stanford University |
| Wesley R Thompson
Institute for Biological Psychiatry, Mental Health Center, Roskilde, Denmark | Paul Davenport
University of Florida |
| Judith L Swain
Singapore Institute for Clinical Science | James Fowler
University of California, San Diego |
| Michelle Craske
University of California, Los Angeles | Tom T Liu
University of California, San Diego |
| Gregory Brown
University of California, San Diego | Susan F Tapert
University of California, San Diego |
| | Angela Yu
University of California, San Diego |

JONATHAN SAVITZ, PH.D.
 Principal Investigator
 Laureate Institute for Brain Research
 Assistant Professor, University of Tulsa
 jsavitz@laureateinstitute.org
 918-502-5104
 antigenlab.org

Dr. Savitz's work focuses on three main areas:

1 Understanding the impact of inflammatory mediators—particularly kynurenine pathway metabolites—on brain structure and function.

2 Developing an experimental model of inflammation in order to evaluate how depressed patients with inflammation differ clinically, immunologically and neurophysiologically from non-depressed patients with inflammation.

3 Identification of potentially pathological autoantibodies in people with depression and psychosis.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Savitz received an undergraduate degree (B.S.) at the University of the Witwatersrand in Johannesburg in psychology and genetics, performed further graduate work in neuropsychology, including a clinical internship, and then completed a Ph.D. on the genetics of bipolar disorder at the University of Cape Town. He subsequently completed a postdoctoral fellowship in the Section of Neuroimaging of Mood and Anxiety Disorders within NIMH's Mood and Anxiety Disorders Program, and is currently an assistant professor at the Laureate Institute for Brain Research and The University of Tulsa. He has trained with two of the most well-known experts in their respective fields, Wayne Drevets (mood disorders, neuroimaging) and Robert Dantzer (psychoneuroimmunology), and has conducted a number of innovative studies that have addressed important gaps in our knowledge regarding the relationship between genes, immunological function, and neuroimaging abnormalities in mood disorders.

Dr. Savitz has published over 50 first or senior author scientific papers and is currently the PI on several grants, including a K01 grant from the NIMH and a National Alliance for Research on Schizophrenia and Depression (NARSAD) Young Investigator Award. He is an associate editor of the scientific journal *Neuroscience Letters*, and serves as a reviewer for numerous European and American grant agencies, including the Mechanisms of Emotion, Stress and Health Study Section (MESH) of the NIH. Dr. Savitz's research aims to delineate the underlying immunological abnormalities associated with major depressive disorder and bipolar disorder, and linking these molecular changes to brain structure and function. In this regard, he is working with Dr. Paulus and Dr. Irwin (UCLA) to initiate an experimental study using endotoxin to safely induce transient inflammation in people suffering from depression. He also is collaborating with Janssen Pharmaceuticals on a project that aims to characterize autoimmune phenomena in people with depression and psychosis.

LAB MEMBERS

- Bart Ford**
Research Assistant
- Harvey Morris**
Research Scientist
- Ashley Reed**
Graduate Student,
University of Tulsa

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Savitz, J., van der Merwe, L., Stein, D.J., Solms, M., Ramesar, R. (2007). Genotype and childhood sexual trauma moderate neurocognitive performance: A possible role for BDNF and ApoE variants. *Biological Psychiatry*. 62, 391-399.

Savitz, J.B., Nugent, A.C., Bogers, W., Roiser, J.P., Bain, E.E., Neumeister, A., Zarate, Jr., C.A., Manji, H.K., Cannon, D.M., Marrett, S., Henn, F., Charney, D.S., Drevets, W.C. (2011). Habenula Volume in Bipolar Disorder and Major Depressive Disorder: A High Resolution MRI Study. *Biological Psychiatry*. 69, 336-343.

Savitz, J., Frank, M.B., Victor, T., Bebak, M., Marino, J.H., Bellgowan, P.S., McKinney, B.A., Bodurka, J., Teague, T.K., Drevets, W.C. (2013). Inflammation and neurological disease-related genes are differentially expressed in depressed patients with mood disorders and correlate with morphometric and functional imaging abnormalities. *Brain, Behavior and Immunity*. 31, 161-171.

Savitz, J.B., Rauch, S. L., Drevets, W.C. (2013). Clinical Application of Brain Imaging for the Diagnosis of Mood Disorders: The current state of play. *Molecular Psychiatry*. 18, 528-539.

Savitz, J., Drevets, W.C., Smith, C.M., Victor, T.A., Wurfel, B.E., Bellgowan, P.S.F., Bodurka, J., Teague, T.K., Dantzer, R. (2015). Putative Neuroprotective and Neurotoxic Kynurenine Pathway Metabolites are Associated with Hippocampal and Amygdalar Volumes in Subjects with Major Depressive Disorder. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 40, 463-471.

Meier, T.B., Drevets, W.C., Wurfel, B.E., Ford, B.N., Morris, H.M., Victor, T.A., Bodurka, J., Teague, T.K., Dantzer, R., Savitz, J. (2016). Relationship between neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites and reductions in right medial prefrontal cortical thickness in major depressive disorder. *Brain Behavior and Immunity*. In press.

COLLABORATORS

- Robert Dantzer, DVM, Ph.D.**
MD Anderson Cancer Center,
University of Texas
- Wayne Drevets, M.D.**
Janssen Pharmaceuticals
- David Goldman, M.D.**
NIAAA
- Mike Irwin, M.D.**
UCLA
- Andrew McKeon, M.B., B.Ch.**
M.D. Mayo Clinic
- Brett McKinney, Ph.D.**
University of Tulsa
- Sheldon Preskorn, M.D.**
University of Kansas
- Kent Teague, Ph.D.**
University of Oklahoma, Tulsa

KYLE SIMMONS, PH.D.
Principal Investigator
Laureate Institute for Brain Research
Associate Professor, University of Tulsa
wksimmons@laureateinstitute.org
918-502-5106

Dr. Simmons's research focuses on three main areas:

1 Why is it that some individuals lose their appetite when they get depressed, and others eat more? Can these changes in eating behavior, or biological markers of how the body and brain use energy, serve as early indicators of depression onset, improvement, or recurrence?

2 What role does brain-body communication play in the development, course and outcome of eating disorders? Can changes in body awareness tell us something about recovery from anorexia nervosa?

3 How does drug craving, such as in nicotine addiction, co-opt brain systems that sense the body's needs and organize behaviors to meet those needs?

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Dr. Simmons completed his master's degree in Clinical Psychology (2001) and his Ph.D. (2005) in Cognitive Psychology at Emory University. He then completed his postdoctoral fellowship under the direction of Dr. Alex Martin in the Laboratory of Brain and Cognition, within the National Institute of Mental Health intramural research program (2005-2009). In 2009, Dr. Simmons was recruited to Tulsa, Oklahoma, where he now directs the Appetitive and Interoceptive Psychopathology Lab at the Laureate Institute for Brain Research.

Dr. Simmons's research falls generally within two domains. One is the neural basis of the conceptual representations underlying humans' food knowledge. In a second domain of research, Dr. Simmons's lab is examining the functional organization of the insular cortex, with particular attention to the insula's role in monitoring the physiological state of the body, otherwise known as interoception.

Both domains of research are highly related, as the insula plays an important role in food motivation and gustatory representation, and interoception is an important component in satiety signaling. The common goal of these two lines of research is to elucidate how the body's homeostatic state influences food reward representation and food-related decision-making, both normatively and in psychiatric illness.

LAB MEMBERS

Jason Avery, Ph.D.
Postdoctoral Associate

Kaiping Burrows, Ph.D.
Postdoctoral Associate

Danielle DeVille
Graduate Student,
University of Tulsa

Kara Kerr
Graduate Student,
University of Tulsa

Casey Mullins
Psychiatric Research Coordinator

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

Depression-related Increases and Decreases in Appetite Reveal Dissociable Patterns of Aberrant Activity in Reward and Interoceptive Neurocircuitry. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*. Simmons WK, Burrows K, Avery JA, Kerr KL, Bodurka J, Savage C, & Drevets WC (in press).

Interoceptive predictions in the brain. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 16, 419-429. *Feldman Barrett L, *Simmons WK (2015). *Indicates equal contribution.

Trait impulsivity is related to ventral ACC and amygdala activity during primary reward anticipation. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*. Kerr K, Avery JA, Barcalow J, Moseman S, Bodurka J, Bellgowan PSF, Simmons WK (2015).

Altered Insula Activity during Visceral Interoception in Weight-Restored Patients with Anorexia Nervosa. Kerr KL, Moseman SE, Avery JA, Bodurka J, Zucker NL, Simmons WK. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2016 Jan;41(2):521-8. doi: 10.1038/npp.2015.174

Major depressive disorder is associated with abnormal interoceptive activity and functional connectivity in the insula. *Biological Psychiatry*. Avery J, Drevets WC, Moseman S, Bodurka J, Barcalow J, Simmons WK (2014).

Category-specific integration of hemostatic signals in the caudal, but not rostral, human insula. *Nature Neuroscience*, 16, 1551-1552. Simmons WK, Rapuano K, Kallman SJ, Ingeholm JE, Miller B, Gotts SJ, Avery JA, Hall KD, & Martin A (2013).

RESEARCH COLLABORATORS

Lisa Feldman Barrett, Ph.D.
Northeastern University

Amanda Bruce, Ph.D.
Department of Psychology, UMKC

William Coberly, Ph.D.
University of Tulsa

Wayne Drevets, M.D.
Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Inc.

Steve Gotts, Ph.D.
Laboratory of Brain and Cognition, NIMH

Kevin Hall, Ph.D.
Laboratory of Biological Modeling, NIDDK

Scott Moseman, M.D.
Laureate Psychiatric Hospital and Clinic

Alex Martin, Ph.D.
Laboratory of Brain and Cognition, NIMH

Brett McKinney, Ph.D.
University of Tulsa

Cary Savage, Ph.D.
Center for Health Behavior Neuroscience, KUMC

Greg Wallace, Ph.D.
George Washington University

Nancy Zucker, Ph.D.
Duke University

Ongoing Studies

If you are interested in participating in any of the studies below, or would like to be considered for future studies, please call our Assessment Team at 918-502-5100 or email info@laureateinstitute.org.

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research

LIBR VOLUNTEERS NEEDED

EARLY ONSET SCHIZOPHRENIA

If you are between the ages of 18-40 and have been diagnosed with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder, you may qualify for this research study. Paid opportunities are available.

Please Call: 918-502-5159

VISTA STUDY: Valacyclovir in early Schizophrenia Treatment, an Adjunct Therapy

Laureate Institute for Brain Research
6655 South Yale Ave, Tulsa, OK 74136

Are You Depressed?

Help us understand how the brain functions in individuals with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD)

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) is studying the biological basis of Major Depressive Disorder (MDD).

We conduct research using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to make images of the brain.

These images help researchers understand how the brain processes emotion and motivation.

MRI is safe, painless, and involves no radiation.

WE NEED YOU

You are eligible if you are:

- male or female
- currently depressed
- ages 18-55
- not currently taking psychiatric medication

Joining this research study provides you with an opportunity to contribute to the understanding of MDD, which affects millions of Americans.

Compensation is provided.

SYMPTOMS OF MDD MAY INCLUDE:

Sadness
Hopelessness
Depressed mood
Problems sleeping
Difficulty concentrating
Lack of motivation

For more information, please call LIBR at: 918-502-5100

Laureate Institute for Brain Research - 6655 South Yale Ave - Tulsa, OK 74136
Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org or email info@laureateinstitute.org

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) aims to discover the biological basis for psychiatric disorders such as Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).

We conduct research using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to make images of the brain.

These images help researchers understand how the brain processes emotion and stress.

MRI is safe, painless, and involves no radiation.

WE NEED YOU

You are eligible if you:

- are male
- a combat veteran
- ages 18-55
- have been diagnosed with PTSD
- are not currently taking psychiatric medication

Joining this research study provides you with an opportunity to contribute to the understanding of PTSD, which affects thousands of veterans.

Compensation is provided.

SYMPTOMS OF PTSD MAY INCLUDE:

Flashbacks
Anxiety
Depression
Insomnia
Nightmares
Irritability
Social Withdrawal

For more information, please call LIBR at 918-502-5159

Laureate Institute for Brain Research - 6655 South Yale Ave - Tulsa, OK 74136
Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org or email PTSDvets@laureateinstitute.org

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

This study aims to explore how effective Behavioral Activation Depression Therapy is in reducing symptoms of depression.

As a participant you will receive 10 weeks of therapy and complete tasks, questionnaires, blood draws, and EEG.

To see what's happening in your brain we will use magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), a very safe technology that takes live images of your brain as it's working. Compensation will be provided.

ABOUT THE THERAPY

Depressive symptoms can impact our day-to-day behavior. Feeling down or depressed, and tired all the time can reduce our desire to seek out and enjoy daily activities. The fewer things we enjoy, the more down or depressed we may feel.

Behavioral activation breaks this vicious cycle by providing opportunities and motivation to engage in more pleasurable and rewarding activities. Behavioral activation also helps us tackle those daunting to-do lists by breaking activities down in a manageable and realistic way.

WE NEED YOU

You may be eligible for this study if you are:

- 18 to 55 years old
- male OR female
- depressed

SYMPTOMS OF DEPRESSION

Loss of pleasure in things you used to enjoy, difficulty sleeping, feeling depressed or blue, changes in weight or appetite, difficulty concentrating, decreased energy or fatigue, moving or talking more slowly.

Laureate Institute for Brain Research - 6655 South Yale Ave, Tulsa, OK, 74136
Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org or email aalanko@laureateinstitute.org

VOLUNTEER for the TULSA 1000 STUDY

Let's bring mental health into the 21st century by helping us develop the world's first "EKG for the psychiatrist"

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

LIBR is a scientific research institute that focuses on discovering brain-based technologies to improve mental health.

LIBR is unique in a number of different ways:

First, it challenges its scientists to think outside the box to come up with game-changing research findings that improve mental health care.

Second, it closely works with the Laureate Psychiatric Clinic and Hospital next door to develop new treatments for psychiatric patients.

Third, it has one of the best brain imaging facilities in the country to study the living brain.

PARTICIPATION

The Tulsa 1000 (or T-1000) study involves five timepoints over the course of one year, including a series of baseline visits and 4 follow-up sessions involving:

- psychiatric assessments
- behavioral testing
- brain imaging scans and tasks
- blood marker testing

All study assessments and procedures will be provided free of charge to you.

You will be paid for your time spent participating in the Tulsa 1000 study.

WE NEED YOU

Qualified volunteers will:

- Be ages 18-55, male or female
- Have problems with depression, anxiety, substance use or eating behavior

OR

- Be free of psychiatric symptoms

Joining this research study helps us move toward our goal of personalizing mental health care.

For more information, please call LIBR at: 918-502-5100

Laureate Institute for Brain Research - 6655 South Yale Ave - Tulsa, OK 74136
Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org or email info@laureateinstitute.org

RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS NEEDED in a Brain Imaging Study of Smoking

The Laureate Institute for Brain Research (LIBR) in Tulsa, OK is currently recruiting adult smokers to better understand how smoking affects brain function. LIBR uses MRI, a noninvasive painless process that uses no medication or radiation.

Participant Requirements:

- No psychiatric medications
- No illegal drug use
- No serious medical conditions
- No history of head trauma

Compensation is provided for time and effort related to participation

For more information please contact:

Casey Mullins
(918) 502-5113
cmullins@laureateinstitute.org

ABOUT OUR RESEARCH

This study aims to explore how anxiety relates to the way we think, feel, and make decisions, as well as how our brain responds to various situations.

As a participant you will complete tasks that trigger parts of your brain involved in decision making and other thought processes.

To see what's happening in your brain, we will use magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), a very safe technology that takes live images of your brain as it's working.

WE NEED YOU

You may be eligible for this study if you:

- Are 18 to 55 years old
- Are male OR female
- Experience high anxiety

OR

- Do not experience any significant mental health symptoms.
- You will be paid for your participation.

SYMPTOMS OF ANXIETY

Fear of or distress in social situations, such as public speaking

Fear of or distress in performance situations, such as taking tests

Exaggerated or persistent worry about a number of different aspects of life

Panic attacks

Muscle tension

Difficulty sleeping

Irritability

Laureate Institute for Brain Research - 6655 South Yale Ave, Tulsa, OK, 74136
Visit us online at www.laureateinstitute.org or email aalanko@laureateinstitute.org

Select Publications

- Avery JA, Kerr KL, Ingeholm JE, Burrows K, Bodurka J, Simmons WK. A common gustatory and interoceptive representation in the human mid-insula. *Hum Brain Mapp*. 2015 Aug;36(8):2996-3006.
- Barrett LF, Simmons WK. Interoceptive predictions in the brain. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2015 Jul;16(7):419-29.
- Cha YH. Mal de débarquement syndrome: new insights. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2015 Apr;1343:63-8.
- Cha YH, Chakrapani S. Voxel Based Morphometry Alterations in Mal de Débarquement Syndrome. *PLoS One*. 2015 Aug 7;10(8):e0135021.
- Feinstein JS, Khalsa SS, Salomons TV, Prkachin KM, Frey-Law LA, Lee JE, Tranel D, Rudrauf D. Preserved emotional awareness of pain in a patient with extensive bilateral damage to the insula, anterior cingulate, and amygdala. *Brain Structure and Function*. 2015, Epub ahead of print.
- He H, Yu Q, Du Y, Vergara V, Victor TA, Drevets WC, Savitz JB, Jiang T, Sui J, Calhoun VD. Resting-state functional network connectivity in prefrontal regions differs between unmedicated patients with bipolar and major depressive disorders. *J Affect Disord*. 2016 Jan 15;190:483-93.
- Kerr KL, Moseman SE, Avery JA, Bodurka J, Zucker NL, Simmons WK. Altered Insula Activity during Visceral Interoception in Weight-Restored Patients with Anorexia Nervosa. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2016 Jan;41(2):521-8.
- Khalsa SS, Craske MG, Li W, Vangala S, Strober M, Feusner JD. Altered interoceptive awareness in anorexia nervosa: effects of meal anticipation, consumption and bodily arousal. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*. 2015.
- Khalsa SS, Rudrauf D, Davidson RJ, Tranel D. The effect of meditation on regulation of internal body states. *Front Psychol*. 2015 Jul 7;6:924.
- Meier TB, Drevets WC, Wurfel BE, Ford BN, Morris HM, Victor TA, Bodurka J, Teague TK, Dantzer R, Savitz J. Relationship between neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites and reductions in right medial prefrontal cortical thickness in major depressive disorder. *Brain Behav Immun*. 2015 Nov 4. pii: S0889-1591(15)30048-9.
- Misaki M, Barzigar N, Zotev V, Phillips R, Cheng S, Bodurka J. Real-time fMRI processing with physiological noise correction - Comparison with off-line analysis. *J Neurosci Methods*. 2015 Dec 30;256:117-21.
- Paulus MP. Pragmatism Instead of Mechanism: A Call for Impactful Biological Psychiatry. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 2015 Jul;72(7):631-2.
- Paulus MP, Aupperle R. Finding the Balance Between Safety and Threat May Hold the Key to Success When Treating PTSD. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2015 Dec 1;172(12):1173-5.
- Savitz J, Dantzer R, Meier TB, Wurfel BE, Victor TA, McIntosh SA, Ford BN, Morris HM, Bodurka J, Teague TK, Drevets WC. Activation of the kynurenine pathway is associated with striatal volume in major depressive disorder. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*. 2015 Dec;62:54-8.
- Savitz J, Drevets WC, Wurfel BE, Ford BN, Bellgowan PS, Victor TA, Bodurka J, Teague TK, Dantzer R. Reduction of kynurenic acid to quinolinic acid ratio in both the depressed and remitted phases of major depressive disorder. *Brain Behav Immun*. 2015 May;46:55-9.
- Simmons WK, Burrows K, Avery JA, Kerr KL, Bodurka J, Savage C, & Drevets WC. Depression-related increases and decreases in appetite reveal dissociable patterns of aberrant activity in reward and interoceptive neurocircuitry. *The American Journal of Psychiatry*. In press.
- Stewart JL, Juavinett AL, May AC, Davenport PW, Paulus MP. Do you feel alright? Attenuated neural processing of aversive interoceptive stimuli in current stimulant users. *Psychophysiology*. 2015 Feb;52(2):249-62.
- Suzuki H, Misaki M, Krueger F, Bodurka J. Neural Responses to Truth Telling and Risk Propensity under Asymmetric Information. *PLoS One*. 2015 Sep 1;10(9):e0137014.
- Young KD, Bellgowan PS, Bodurka J, Drevets WC. Autobiographical deficits correlate with gray matter volume in depressed and high risk participants. *Soc Cogn Affect Neurosci*. 2015 Nov;10(11):1588-95.
- Young KD, Bellgowan PS, Bodurka J, Drevets WC. Functional neuro-imaging correlates of autobiographical memory deficits in subjects at risk for depression. *Brain Sci*. 2015 Apr 24;5(2):144-64.
- Young KD, Siegle GJ, Bodurka J, Drevets WC. Amygdala Activity During Autobiographical Memory Recall in Depressed and Vulnerable Individuals: Association With Symptom Severity and Autobiographical Overgenerality. *Am J Psychiatry*. 2016 Jan 1;173(1):78-89.
- Yuan H, Ding L, Zhu M, Zotev V, Phillips R, Bodurka J. Reconstructing Large-Scale Brain Resting-State Networks from High-Resolution EEG: Spatial and Temporal Comparisons with fMRI. *Brain Connect*. 2015 Oct 13.

LIBR

Laureate Institute for Brain Research

6655 South Yale Avenue

Tulsa, OK 74136

918-502-5100

laureateinstitute.org

info@laureateinstitute.org

 facebook.com/LIBResearch